

Holistic design optimisation applied to a wind propelled cruise vessel

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Abstract. The application of wind propulsion in commercial shipping is gaining traction. Most installations nowadays add wind propulsion to an existing ship design, keeping the rest of the design unaltered. The vessels often operate as motorsailers, using the engine in conditions where wind is not favourable, as delays in arrival times are not accepted. It is an open question which aspects of a new build design might be altered to further improve the benefits of wind propulsion. This topic is investigated previously for a wind propelled bulk carrier [1] and here for a cruise vessel by applying the CREATOR methodology, developed alongside the EU project OPTIWISE. In this method the early ship design is approached as a holistic optimisation problem, using predictive models for as many aspects of the ship design as feasible. For this application the resistance, propeller-engine matching, hull and rudder forces, anti-heeling devices, anti-drift devices, added resistance in waves, windage and a simplified general arrangement and weight estimation are considered. The performance including wind propulsion for each design candidate was evaluated for a large number of combinations of ship speed and wind conditions. These results were weighted using the probability obtained from voyage calculations with weather re-routing. The optimum design is obtained using surrogate models for the various objectives and constraints in combination with a multi-objective optimisation algorithm. It was shown this way that primarily the lower design speed leads to different optimum main dimensions rather than the addition of wind propulsion.

Keywords: *Ship design, Wind propulsion, CFD, Hydrodynamics, CREATOR.*

1 Introduction

During the EU project OPTIWISE it was attempted to redefine the design process as a mathematical optimisation problem, modelling various aspects of the design to quantify the performance. This allows to explore the benefit of a holistic approach to ship design. This was demonstrated for three ship types with substantial wind propulsion integrated in a new build concept design. Earlier, the results of a bulk carrier have been published in [1]. It was found that the initial main particulars are also optimum for a wind propelled bulk carrier. Slight improvements were obtained by increasing the propeller diameter which also holds for the vessel without wind propulsion. Changing the propeller to a Controllable Pitch Propeller (CPP) yielded equal performance with wind propulsion, only regaining the loss in efficiency at the design pitch compared to a Fixed Pitch Propeller (FPP). Here the results of a cruise vessel with wing sails are described. Starting with the optimisation approach applied to the design, followed by the used modelling for the various components and finally the results of the design exercise and the overall performance relative to a virtual baseline vessel.

2 Optimisation methodology applied to ship design

The design process is defined as a mathematical optimisation problem as shown in Equation (1). An objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$ is defined, depending on a vector of design variables \mathbf{x} . In addition equality $h(\mathbf{x})$ and inequality constraints $g(\mathbf{x})$ are used. Both the objective as the constraints are derived from the responses obtained from evaluating the ship design candidate defined by these design variables. A robust and efficient evaluation of the responses for each design candidate is one of the key challenges and described in more detail in chapter 3.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimise } f(\mathbf{x}) \\ & \text{subject to } h(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \\ & \quad \quad \quad g(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

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During the study two objectives are used, the average required shaft power with wind propulsion in operational conditions and the average shaft power of the same vessel without wind propulsion in trial condition. Multiple constraints are used as summarised in Table 1. The difference between the hydrostatics and weight estimation is used with a tolerance reflecting room for variations in the weight distribution. A constraint on the stability criteria is used in the form of limits on the metacentric height range. This can be seen as a simplified inclusion of the intact (IS CODE 2008) and damage stability criteria (SOLAS Chapter II-1). Limits on the main particulars are included for the length, beam and air draught, following vessel size limits from the original Panama canal. The constraint for the air draught is neglected to give more freedom to the optimisation. The draught is the traditional maximum draught for the cruising area of the Mediterranean Sea in the summer and Caribbean in the winter. The number of passengers is set to that of the parent design and is not varied. This parameter is used for the required accommodation at a given luxury level as described in more detail in section 3.1 and influences the main particulars through it.

Table 1. Constraints used in the optimisation

Difference in displacement	≤ 0.5	% of weight
Difference in longitudinal centre of buoyancy	≤ 2.5	% of LCB from APP
Metacentric height	d	m
Length overall	≤ 294	m
Moulded beam	≤ 32.25	m
Draught	≤ 9.5	m
Air draught	≤ 57.91	m
Number of passengers	Equal to parent design	-

The optimisation problem is approached using a Design of Experiments (DoE), generating a set of samples spanning the design space. The samples are generated using the Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) method. The number of samples is determined using the theoretical minimum required for a second order fit as given by Equation (2), based on this, 24 designs are used for this study. The design space for the hull is given in Table 2 using non-dimensional parameters in combination with the displacement to give the design absolute dimensions.

$$N_{samples} = \frac{(N_{design\ variables} + order)!}{N_{design\ variables}! \cdot order!} \quad (2)$$

Table 2. Design space for the hull

Slenderness	$\frac{L_{OS}}{\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}}$	6.0 up to 10.0	
Block coefficient	C_B	0.50 up to 0.70	
Relative LCB from amidship	$\frac{LCB}{L_{OS}}$	-5 up to 3	%
Beam to draught ratio	$\frac{B}{T}$	2.4 up to 6.0	
Displacement	Δ	15000 up to 30000	t

Each of the designs in the design of experiments is evaluated using the so-called CREATOR method. This method uses a python framework to define various aspects of the designs, described in building blocks, and perform evaluations, like the prediction for the performance with wind propulsion. From the resulting responses a surrogate model is constructed for the various objectives and constraints. The quality of the surrogate models is tested with leave one out cross-validation. In general Kriging methods give good results. For some of the responses linear regression methods give better results and are used instead.

The surrogates are used in a multi objective optimisation algorithm. For the study the NSGAI [2] algorithm is used with, when relevant, a modification to handle discrete variables. The optimisation algorithm gives satisfactory results as the performance of the re-evaluated designs is close to the by the algorithm predicted performance and improved from the parent design. No other optimisation algorithms are compared for this reason.

3 Predictive models

For the optimisation methodology it is required to define predictive models for various components of the vessel. As the aim is to evaluate the merit of a holistic optimisation approach, this should include a wide range of components. For the ship type the general arrangement, weight estimation and stability are assumed to be of great importance, guiding the selection of main particulars. Economic factors related to both the investment and operation are known to be important and interesting, but it was not feasible to capture them in predictive models. Instead, the operational profile was kept constant and the effect of the investment was left for qualitative assessment. Furthermore, various components affecting the power requirements are included. The final step towards fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions is done in a simplified fashion using constant factors. This to separate the design of the power and energy systems from the optimisation described here.

3.1 General arrangement and weight estimation

To generate the arrangement and weight model, the general arrangement of a parent design is analysed to identify the most relevant compartment types onboard. For each of the compartment types, a parameter is selected on which the compartment area is depending (number of passengers, length of ship, etc.). A total of 40 compartment types are identified. An example of the resulting table is shown in Table 3. The spaces with air conditioning are indicated and used to determine the area taken by the air-conditioning equipment (HVAC system). The areas below main deck, mainly used for propulsion and other main ship systems, are not considered in the parametric arrangement model. It is implicitly assumed that there will be sufficient space to accommodate the machinery, consumables, and other technical equipment.

Table 3. Example of the compartment categories and their required area based on the parent vessel.

Category	Air Conditioned [Y/N]	Dependent on (parameter)	Specific area	
			Value	Unit
Bar and restaurants	Y	No. passengers	X.XX	m ² /pax
Cabin balcony	N	No. pax cabin w/ balcony	XX.X	m ² /cabin with balcony
Captain/chief eng. Cabin	Y	Independent	XX.X	m ²
...

The area coefficients are valid for ships of similar type, namely luxury cruise ships. However, the luxury level can be adjusted by varying the cabin area, public space area, outdoor space area and the crew to passenger ratio. The coefficients for a given luxury level are used to determine the number of passengers that can be accommodated together with the internal volume and related Gross Tonnage (GT).

The mass properties[†] and the height to main and other decks are obtained from linear regressions using cruise ship data from Significant Ships magazines in combination with own data available at MARIN. A total of 52 ships are included in the analysis, consisting of sea-going cruise ships, mostly of medium to large size, built between 1990 and 2022. Figure 1 shows an example of two of these regressions, used to determine the mass properties.

Figure 1. Example of the regressions used for the lightship weight (left) and depth to main deck (right).

[†] weight, center of gravity, moments of inertia and inertia radii

Based on the superstructure shape of several reference cruise ships, the depth to main deck (D_{main}), depth to upper deck[‡] (D_{up}), depth to top deck[§] (D_{top}), longitudinal coordinate of the aftmost end of the superstructure ($x_{sup,aft}$), longitudinal coordinate of the foremost end of the superstructure ($x_{sup,fwd}$), angle between the horizontal and the aft end of the superstructure (α_{aft}), angle between the horizontal and the forward end of the superstructure (α_{fwd}) and the angle between the horizontal and the stem (α_{stem}), were used to model the geometry of the superstructure. As shown in Figure 2 these parameters can be combined to replicate the shape of the superstructure of different types of cruise ships.

Figure 2. Example of the different superstructure parameters of a conventional cruise (below) and a more luxurious cruise ship (top).

To generate a superstructure candidate, the algorithm sets first the depth to main deck using a regression. Next, starting from this deck, decks are generated following the input stem angle assuming a height of 3.0m for the decks in the hull. This is repeated until the depth to upper deck is reached. Then, the superstructure decks are generated following the given superstructure angles assuming a height of 2.8m for the decks in the superstructure. This process continues until the target number of decks is reached, or until the forward and aft end of a deck meet, indicating that no more decks can be created.

Once all the decks are defined, the enclosed volume of the ship, air draught, frontal area, and other parameters are calculated. With the enclosed volume the GT is determined, which is used to calculate the lightship weight using a regression. In addition, the wind propulsors are located with a fixed minimum spacing between them starting from the most forward feasible position. The mass properties (total weight, inertia moments and inertia radii of the vessel) are corrected for the wind propulsors. Based on the total deck area and the required specific area per passenger, the total number of passengers is obtained. In figure 3, a side view of a generated vessel is presented, showing the decks and indicating the centre of gravity.

The number of decks and fore and aft angles of the superstructure are not included in the design variables of the design optimisation problem, but determined for each design candidate. For a range of deck numbers, the superstructure angles with the minimum difference between weight and displacement are obtained using an optimisation algorithm, which a constraint that the aft angle should be at least 1.5 times the fore angle. If for multiple number of decks the weight discrepancy is less than the allowed range, the candidate with a metacentric height higher than the minimum and the lowest air draught is selected.

[‡] Defined as the uppermost deck of the hull

^{§§} Defined as the uppermost continuous deck of the superstructure

Figure 3. Example of the generated superstructure model, sail configuration and centre of gravity of a generated vessel.

3.2 Hull form geometry and hydrostatics

For each of the design candidates a 3D hull model is generated and used for the evaluation of the hydrostatic properties and high fidelity hydrodynamic performance evaluations. An alternative low fidelity approach would be to use empirical formulations for estimations of the hydrostatic parameters and hydrodynamic performance, removing the requirement for the generation of 3D models. For this study the high fidelity approach was used.

The hull forms are generated by performing a Lackenby shift function on the sections of a manually drawn parent hull form combined with scaling of the main dimensions of the hull. The dimensions, target displaced volume and target longitudinal centre of buoyancy are derived from the design variables given in Table 2. After scaling the hull form, the volume and longitudinal centre of buoyancy are set by determining the shift function using McNaull's method [3] and applying the Lackenby shift on the 3D hull model. The vessel has a centre skeg that is scaled which the length of the vessel and included in the bare hull. The process is automated using Rhino Grasshopper in combination with proprietary tools developed at MARIN.

Using a reasonably optimised parent hull form avoids generation of hydrodynamically non-optimal hull forms. It is well known that a given set of hydrostatic parameters does not relate to a unique definition of a hull form. Multiple hull forms can match the parameters of which generally the one with minimal resistance or power requirement is sought. The methodology can easily be extended by adding local hull form modifications as additional design variables to move closer to this hydrodynamic optimum. During the current study this last step was omitted, assuming that the parent hull form was close enough to the optimum.

3.3 Resistance and propulsion

The resistance of the bare hull is determined from RANS viscous flow calculations (CFD) of the generated hull form at three speeds. The calculations are repeated with the actuator disk model to get an approximation of the thrust deduction. An example of one of the results is shown in Figure 4. Using these points, an empirical resistance prediction based on the hydrostatic parameters is calibrated to derive the resistance curve over the entire speed range.

The appendage resistance is added using the form factor approach as given in Equation (3). The form factor is derived from CFD calculations of the appended parent hull. The appendage area is scaled with the length from the parent hull. A resistance allowance is added using MARIN's basis correlation allowance using Equation (4). A correction factor is determined on the nominal wake fraction and the thrust deduction to match the known values of the appended parent hull.

$$R_{app} = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_s^2 S_{app} (1 + k_2)_{eq} \quad (3)$$

$$R_A = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_s^2 S C_A \quad (4)$$

$$C_A = 0.0058 (L_{OS} + 100)^{-0.16} - 0.00196$$

Figure 4. Example of the results from one of the resistance CFD calculations, showing the dynamic pressure coefficient on the left and wave pattern on the right.

The resulting resistance curve and propeller-hull interaction coefficients are used to determine the propeller and engine particulars. The maximum propeller diameter is limited by the hull due to the available space and assumed required clearance of 30% of the diameter. The optimum propeller diameter and rotation rate is selected using the MARIN C-series at a design speed of 15 knots assuming constant pitch operation. This decoupled approach of optimising the propeller particulars seems justified as in [4] it was shown that optimising the propeller for the full operational profile including wind propulsion yielded only very limited gains.

The engine particulars are determined by applying a sea and engine margin as described for instance in [5]. As for this vessel type the safe-return to port criteria (SOLAS Chapter II-2 reg. 21) is generally leading for the installed power, the engine margin was changed up to the point where it was satisfied. The criteria recommends a sustained ship speed of 6 knots in 8 Beaufort of wind. The related sea state was derived using NATO Stanag 4194 Annex D. Both head wind and head waves are assumed. The added resistance from wind and waves is determined using the predictive models described later. For the safe-return to port evaluation constant rotation rate operation is assumed. An example of the resulting open-water diagram, describing the propeller performance, and propeller engine matching is shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6. In this case the engine margin is reduced, matching the minimum installed power for the safe return to port criteria.

Figure 5. Example of the open water diagram with operational points over the speed range in calm water obtained for one of the designs.

Figure 6. Example of the intersection between the engine diagram and propeller curve for one of the designs. The trial condition is shown on the left and the safe return to port condition on the right.

3.4 Hull forces

The hull forces were also evaluated using CFD for all the designs, neglecting the contribution of the free surface. It was shown that, in contrast to perception, a coarse grid approach gave very close agreement to a fine grid result at much reduced calculation cost. Generally, the observed viscous flow separation is one of the arguments to use very refined grids. This is shown in Figure 7 for the small leeway angles relevant for the sailing equilibrium with wind propulsion. These results are transformed to the more relevant lift, drag and centre of lateral resistance (CLR) which is the application point of the side force. It is observed that the effect of appendages, here without movable devices like the rudders and anti-drift fins, is however of major importance. As it was not feasible to include scaled and with the flow aligned appendages in an automated fashion the bare hull results are corrected using the difference in manoeuvring coefficients determined from the parent hull using Equation (5). The point at zero leeway is shown but more accurately captured by the resistance curve, therefore it is not used in the final predictive model.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Longitudinal force} \quad C_X &= \frac{F_X}{\frac{1}{2} \rho V_s^2 L T} && + \text{forward} \\
 \text{Size force} \quad C_Y &= \frac{F_Y}{\frac{1}{2} \rho V_s^2 L T} && + \text{to port} \\
 \text{Yawing moment} \quad C_N &= \frac{M_Z}{\frac{1}{2} \rho V_s^2 L^2 T} && + \text{Counterclockwise looking from above}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Figure 7. Example of the hull forces at small leeway angles for one of the designs, comparing the results between coarse and fine grid CFD calculations and bare hull and appended.

3.5 Rudder

The rudder is modelled using the MARIN rudder model as described in [6]. The predictive model describes the rudder performance based on an aspect ratio dependent lift and drag curve model using linear lift and related induced drag with a coefficient prescribing the maximum lift coefficient in combination with cross-flow drag. The effective inflow velocity and angle is determined using flow straightening of the hull, a wake fraction and a model for the propeller induced velocities. A coefficient is used for the rudder-to-hull interaction of the side force. During the study the default coefficients are used, except for the parasitic drag (C_{D0}) which is set to zero to avoid double counting with the resistance curve and thrust deduction coefficients which also include the rudder contribution.

3.6 Seakeeping

The added resistance in waves is calculated from quadratic transfer functions (QTF) obtained using MARIN's 3D panel Rankine source method SEACAL for a range of GM values per design. The effect of GM is captured using a surrogate model of the QTF database as described in detail in [7]. In addition, the seakeeping calculation of the parent design is used to determine the seakeeping criteria for comfort and safety levels onboard the ship in the weather re-routing calculations as described in section 3.8.

3.7 Aerodynamics and wind propulsion

The windage was evaluated using steady RANS CFD calculations for the parent and optimised design. The calculations are performed including the atmospheric boundary layer imposed using a 1/9 power law, as prescribed by the ITTC [8], at zero ship speed. The forces are made non-dimensional using the definitions given in Equation 6. During the optimisation the windage coefficients of the parent design are used with scaled frontal, lateral area and reference height. For the final design a 3D model for the superstructure was drawn and the windage coefficients are re-evaluated. The ship and superstructure are shown for an example of one of the CFD calculations in Figure 8. The resulting windage coefficients are shown in Figure 9. It can be noted that mainly in headwinds the windage coefficient increases leading to an underestimation during the optimisation, this is expected for the more blunt shape. The side force and heeling moment coefficient are slightly increased.

Longitudinal force	$C_X = \frac{F_X}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A W S_{z=h}^2 A_F}$	+ <i>forward</i>	
Side force	$C_Y = \frac{F_Y}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A W S_{z=h}^2 A_{LAT}}$	+ <i>to port</i>	
Heeling moment	$C_K = \frac{F_X H}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A W S_{z=h}^2 A_{LAT}}$	+ <i>Clockwise looking from astern</i>	(6)
Yawing moment	$C_N = \frac{F_X L_{pp}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A W S_{z=h}^2 A_{LAT}}$	+ <i>Counterclockwise looking from above</i>	

Figure 8. Example of the results of an aerodynamic CFD calculation. The dynamic pressure coefficient and streamlines through the positions of the sails are shown for the optimised new-build concept at an apparent wind angle of 45 degrees.

Figure 9. Windage coefficients shown for the parent ship and superstructure and the re-evaluated windage coefficients for the optimised design.

The SolidSail system, developed by Chantiers de l'Atlantique, consists of a rigid foldable main sail with a furling jib. The system can be tilted to reduce the air draught. The main particulars are given in Table 4 and a visualisation of the system in Figure 10.

Table 4. Main particulars of the SolidSail system

Height	74.0	m
Tilted height	31.5	m
Lateral area	1430	m ²

Figure 10. Visualisation of the solid ail system in upright and tilted position.

The aerodynamic performance of the wind propulsion is derived from standalone performance curves of the SolidSail system in combination with MARIN's model for aerodynamic interaction effects. The method defines the effective wind as experienced by the wind propulsors based on three contributions: the location in the atmospheric boundary layer, the disturbed wind from the ship and superstructure and the induced wind from the interaction between the wind propulsors [9]. The disturbed wind is obtained from the CFD calculations using line probes at the location of the wind propulsors. The induced wind from a non-linear linear lifting line method [10] with a modification for using 3D lift and drag curves of the wind propulsion device directly.

The effect of the disturbed wind is illustrated in Figure 11. Due to the flow over the ship and superstructure, the apparent wind direction shifts to more beam wind in both the bow and stern quartering wind conditions. This generally has a favourable effect on the performance. The method results in a matrix of force coefficients depending on the true wind speed and angle. An example of the driving force coefficient obtained at one of the true wind speeds is shown in Figure 12. It can be observed that the foremost sail has a slight increase in driving force and the aftmost sail a slight decrease as is generally expected for a sail system. The force matrix is used with a depowering method in the performance prediction of the optimised vessel. During the optimisation, the aerodynamic interaction effects are neglected and the standalone performance curve was used instead.

Figure 11. Example of the effect of disturbed wind on the effective wind experienced by the wind propulsors obtained for the optimised new build vessel shown for the three wind propulsors, one being most aft and three most forward.

Figure 12. Example of the predicted polar of the driving force coefficient with optimised settings for each of the wind propulsors for a TWS of 7.5 m/s and a ship speed of 12 knots.

3.8 Performance prediction with wind propulsion

The performance of the vessel is determined by predicting the performance for a list of conditions, defined as combinations of ship speed, true wind speed and true wind angle. For each point the CO₂ emissions of the vessel are minimised while balancing the thrust, side force, yawing moment and heeling moment using equality constraints (4 Degrees of Freedom approach). In MARIN's Power Prediction Program (PPP) Sailfish a Sequential Least Squares Quadratic Programming (SLSQP) solver is used for this. For the CPP propeller the optimum off design pitch and rotation rate is selected at each condition. The controls of the wind propulsors are optimised. Aspects of the design are described using the predictive models.

The resulting performance polars are multiplied with the averaged wind statistics over the operational profile as illustrated in Figure 13. It should be noted that the example is not the current design. The wind statistics are obtained using weather re-routing with MARIN's implementation of the Lazy Theta* algorithm using the performance polars of the parent vessel over the operational profile shown in Figure 14. During the re-routing conditions with excessive green water, less than 5% of the wave encounters, and motion illness rating, less than 5 on a scale from 0-100, are avoided. The obtained wind statistics are less favourable compared to the wind over global shipping routes with an average wind speed of 5.0 m/s compared to 6.5 m/s and more bow quartering and stern winds. This is caused by the sailing area in the Mediterranean and Caribbean with short voyages reducing the room for weather re-routing.

Figure 13. Example of the methodology to determine the performance of a wind propelled vessel using performance polars and wind statistics (performance and wind statistics not for the current design).

Figure 14. Overview of the West Mediterranean (top left), East Mediterranean (middle top), Caribbean (top right), and Atlantic crossing (bottom) routes selected for the operational analysis.

4 Results

Each of the designs is evaluated using the CREATOR method. During this step various aspects of the design are described, predictive models are defined and the performance in calm water and in operational condition with wind propulsion is evaluated. Surrogate models are generated for the objectives and constraints based on the calculated responses. Using the optimisation algorithm, the optimum designs are obtained balancing the objective of minimum power in trial condition at the operational speed and minimum average power with wind propulsion over the operational profile in transit. This is done while respecting the constraints given in Table 1.

The results are shown in Figure 15. The black points indicate the evaluated designs and the red points the pareto front balancing the two objectives. As it can be observed, the best design has both optimal performance in trial condition and with wind propulsion. Instead of the common pareto front, a point is observed and the evaluated designs fall on a more or less linear trend towards this point. This is an interesting result, because it is generally expected that vessels with a large contribution of wind propulsion would benefit from selecting different main particulars to improve the losses in the sailing equilibrium. This seems not the case.

Figure 15. Evaluated design candidates (shown in black) and obtained pareto front (shown in red) showing the trade-off between optimising for the shaft power in trial condition and over the operational profile including wind propulsion.

A subset of the main particulars from the selected optimum design is compared to the parent design in Table 5. It can be observed that the vessel is shortened with an increased beam and draught at the minimum block coefficient of the design space. The design was re-evaluated in the same way as the other designs and various performance indices are compared in Table 6. It can be observed that the two objectives are well predicted by the optimisation algorithm using the surrogate models based on the limited set of evaluated designs. The difference between the weight estimation and hydrostatics are slightly larger. As the optimum design is already close to the constraints, the re-evaluated design falls just over these limits.

Table 5. Subset of main particulars of the optimised design in relation to the parent design

		Parent design	Optimised design	Unit
Length overall submerged	L_{OS}	~210	149.5	m
Beam	B	~25	28.6	m
Draught	T	~5.40	7.21	m
Block coefficient	C_B	Not disclosed	0.50	

Table 6. Comparison of the predicted and re-evaluated optimum design

	Predicted optimum	Re-evaluated
Resistance - 12 knots, trial condition	<i>Not evaluated</i>	-12%
Shaft power - 12 knots, trial condition	-18%	-18%
Shaft power - operational profile without wind propulsion	<i>Not evaluated</i>	-15%
Shaft power - operational profile with wind propulsion	-18%	-17%
Difference between weight and displacement	0.3%	1.6%
Difference between LCG and LCB	2.4%	3.2%

The optimisation design approach directs towards the optimum design, but does not explain why this design is favoured. This is studied by first comparing the resistance and speed-power curve of the parent design and optimised design as shown in Figure 16. It is observed that the optimised design has lower resistance up to about 16 knots. This is due to lower wetted surface area and related frictional resistance at the cost of higher wave making resistance at the higher speed range. The speed-power curve shows a larger difference and a cross over at around 18 knots. This is related to an increased propeller efficiency as the increased draught allows for a larger diameter.

Figure 16. Comparison of the resistance curve and speed-power curve in trial condition between the parent and optimised design.

The contribution of various resistance components in operational condition including effects of wind propulsion are compared in Figure 17. These are obtained using weighting with the distribution of wind statistics encountered during transit. It can be observed that the relative contribution of the windage, added resistance in waves and additional appendage resistance under leeway has increased from 4.2% to 7.8%. However, the decrease in resistance and increase in propulsive efficiency has outweighed this relative increase.

Figure 17. Relative contribution of the resistance components for both the parent and optimised design during transit including effects of wind propulsion.

It should be noted that the vessel, although having a substantial contribution of wind propulsion to the shaft power as shown in Figure 18, is still assumed to operate primarily as a motor sailing vessel. Due to the constraint in arrival time it is not feasible to beat to windward between bow and close-hauled wind angles. It is likely that removing this constraint leads to both a wider range of operational ship speeds and increases the importance of reducing losses in the sailing equilibrium. As discussed in section 3.8 the wind statistics over the operational profile are worse compared to global shipping routes even after weather re-routing which reduces the achieved savings.

Figure 18. Effect of wind propulsion on the average shaft power of the optimised design over the operational profile considering only transit mode.

Apart from the application of wind propulsion, also the operational speed is lowered and dual fuel diesel/LNG-electric propulsion is used instead of diesel fuel with direct transmission. It is therefore not relevant to compare the shaft power used for propulsion between the design with and without wind propulsion in transit mode. Instead, the CO₂ emissions over the entire operation are assessed using an operational analysis and compared to the average operational performance of cruise vessels with similar GT. The operational profile as described in paragraph 3.8 has been used. Based on the typical operation of a cruise ship, the following main tasks were defined:

- Harbor: Ship at quay
- Manoeuvring: Ship sailing at low speed and using thrusters.
- Transit: Ship sailing at service speed with all hotel consumers
- Anchoring: Ship anchored near shore

For each task the average propulsion and hotel load is defined, and using the chain efficiency the total power demanded at the main switchboard is calculated. The chain efficiency accounts for the losses in the electric system. The propulsive power is obtained from the evaluation of the vessel with wind propulsion using CREATOR weighting with the long term wind statistics along the sailing routes. For the electric transmission an efficiency of 90% is assumed, and for the hotel and auxiliary load 95%. It should be noted that no shore power was considered in the study for the sake of simplicity. The fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions are obtained using an assumed constant specific fuel consumption (SFC in g/kWh) and conversion factor (CF in tCO₂/tFuel) as shown in Equation (7) in combination with time weighting.

$$\begin{aligned}
 FC_i &= SFC_i \cdot P_{total,i} \cdot \Delta t \\
 CO_{2i} &= FC_i \cdot CF
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{7}$$

In Table 7 a summary of the results is presented. The CO₂ emissions are calculated for the optimised design with and without wind propulsion assuming operation on diesel fuel. In addition, the emissions are shown for operation on LNG. The conversion factor is taken from the EEDI calculation guidelines (MEPC.308(74)) and the specific fuel consumption based on the values at 85% MCR of engines of similar size.

To compare the CO₂ emissions, a reference benchmark had to be established. For that, the data from the MRV** system of the European Union is used. The EU MRV system collects and reports data for CO₂ emissions for ships above 5000 GT engaged in EU-related voyages (i.e., sailing from, to and between ports of member states). A regression analysis was carried between the values of CO₂ per nautical mile and the gross tonnage, resulting in the diagram presented in Figure 19. As the optimised design has a gross tonnage of 25000 GT, substituting this GT value in the regression formula the following reference value for the CO₂ emissions was selected:

$$\text{Reference } CO_2 \text{ emissions} = 425.7 \frac{\text{kgCO}_2}{\text{nm}}$$

** <https://mrv.emsa.europa.eu/#public/emission-report>

Figure 19. Regression analysis of MRV data of CO₂ emissions per nautical mile versus gross tonnage (GT).

It is observed that a large reduction of the CO₂ emissions is achieved relative to the benchmark. A large part of the savings of 45% is obtained from the operation with lower ship speed as observed from the diesel operation without wind propulsion. It should be noted that there are a few ships in the MRV database that also display these low emissions. This is either because they sail at lower speeds or they have implemented propulsion systems with reduced the fuel consumption (e.g., battery hybrid). The relative contribution of wind propulsion diminishes from the saving of 24% in shaft power due to the contribution of the hotel and auxiliary power in both transit and other modes. Furthermore, the higher reference of the MRV database reduces the percent point savings. Finally, the effect of using LNG is shown which, using the assumed conversion factor, reduces CO₂ emissions further to almost 65%.

Table 7. Results summary of the fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions for the operational analysis.

Item	Unit	New design without wind propulsion (diesel)	New design with wind propulsion (diesel)	New design with wind propulsion (LNG)	MRV database
Propulsion type	-	Diesel-electric	Diesel-electric	Diesel-electric	
Fuel type	-	Diesel/gasoil	Diesel/gasoil	LNG	
Lower heating value of fuel	kJ/kg	42700	42700	48000	
Fuel conversion factor CF	tCO ₂ /tFuel	3.206	3.206	2.75	
Specific Fuel consumption of engines	g/kWh	190	190	160.8	
Required propulsion power	kW	2265	1718	1718	
Hotel load	kW	1600	1600	1600	
Shore power in larger harbours	kW	1600	1600	1600	
Chain efficiency for propulsion units	-	0.90	0.90	0.90	
Chain efficiency for hotel consumers	-	0.95	0.95	0.95	
Annual values					
Average speed in transit	kn	11.83	11.83	11.83	
Total distance travelled	nm	76782	76782	76782	
CO ₂ emissions in transit per nautical mile	kgCO ₂ /nm	203.0	175.1	127.1	
CO ₂ emissions in harbour per nautical mile	kgCO ₂ /nm	31.4	31.4	22.8	
Total CO ₂ emissions per nautical mile	kgCO ₂ /nm	234.5	206.5	149.9	425.7
Saving in CO ₂ emissions per nautical mile	%	44.9	51.5	64.8	0.0

5 Conclusions and recommendations

It is demonstrated that a holistic optimisation approach can be useful to obtain large shaft power savings by finding more optimal main particulars. For the cruise ship a reduction of 20% in shaft power from the parent design is possible by modifying the main particulars. A further reduction of 25% is obtained from wind propulsion. As these savings only contribute in transit mode the relative savings reduce when considering the full operational profile with hotel and auxiliary load and manoeuvring and harbour operation. For this design other design choices, like the slow sailing speed and fuel type result in larger savings bringing the total to 65% savings relative to the average performance of cruise vessels of this size.

Furthermore, it was observed that, contrary to general expectations, the same main particulars are optimal for calm water performance as performance with wind propulsion. The savings in resistance and shaft power outweigh the increase in windage, added resistance in waves and losses in the sailing equilibrium. The outcome might change when the transit time is more flexible, allowing the vessel to beat upwind instead of motor sailing. In upwind conditions losses in the sailing equilibrium are more important.

Some simplifications on the modelling and choices in the design space could have some impact on the obtained results, like the wind propulsor positioning, exclusion of the appendages in the geometry for high fidelity resistance evaluations and the neglect of engine envelope limits. The general arrangement is only included in a simplified fashion and for the shorter vessel less space might be available below decks to place the machinery. The intact and damage stability criteria were not assessed during the study, only a limit on the metacentric height was taken into account.

Even though the holistic optimisation approach yielded interesting insights, the objectives and constraints used in such an approach will likely never take all design criteria into account and the quantitative modelling of ship components can be time consuming and costly. This is especially the case when using high-fidelity models such as CFD. As the objective is only on shaft power savings, other aspects like comfort and safety and aesthetics of the design are not directly taken into account. It is likely that aesthetics also drive the design for a luxury cruise vessel and the obtained optimised design is visually less appealing and more similar to a regular cruise vessel.

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